

A Debonding on demand technique to recycle ABS from automotive: Effect on the mechanical properties

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1. Abstract

The research presented here focuses on the study of recyclability and the mechanical performance (tensile and impact strength) of painted Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene (ABS). A commercial debonding-on-demand technique by triggering paint additives by temperature (INDAR®) was studied to allow an easy re-processability of the material. A comprehensive assessment was done to determine the impact of debonding methods on the final properties of the recycled polymer. The exposure to such conditions led to a decrease of the tensile by 13% and maintained the impact strength. The use of a debonding technique to recycle automotive-user parts was shown to decrease the mechanical performance. The crosshatch test showed that the primer resisted the ageing test correctly. A full process of recycling was developed to recycle ABS parts. The material after one recycling cycle (ABS1CR) showed a lost about 17% of the tensile strength and maintained its impact strength whereas after a second cycle (ABS2CR) lost 19% of the tensile properties but only lost 6.5% of the impact properties. The continuous degradation process by reprocessing toward the presence of coating impurities by previous cleaning and reprocessed material, explained this result. These results provide an insight of the material performance after a full recycling process of coated parts for the automotive industry.

2. Introduction

Nowadays, the automotive sector uses a big number of plastic materials. The increasing concerns about energy consumption led to lightweighting of the vehicles to reduce the fuel used and that is mainly accomplished by the increasing use of plastic materials. Several polymers are used in automotive depending on the final application. These include Polypropylene (PP), polyurethane (PU), and polyvinyl chloride (PVC) as the most used ones. However, when high performance, interior design and comfort plays a major role, other polymers like Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene (ABS) are highlighted. ABS is one of the most important materials for the automotive sector. It is

a plastic material that combines good processability and impact strength with high toughness and resistance to chemicals [1]. For that reason, it is widely used in the bumpers, wheel covers and instrumental panels of the car [2].

Commonly, plastic components are employed in visible applications, where design plays an important factor in the consumer's decision and for that, they are commonly coated with paints or varnishes that improve their appearance and their resistance to external agents. Despite that, they add an additional stone on the recyclability path, as they are designed to be strongly attached to the substrate surface and resist aggressive conditions [3, 4]. On top of that, additives such as flame retardants, UV stabilizers and others, are commonly used and includes organophosphorus and/or hazardous halogenated compounds. These materials are considered impurities and may potentially trigger several polymer degradation mechanisms [5]. On the other hand, studies showed that coating impurities decrease the mechanical properties of the recycled material, preventing its use on demanding applications [6, 7, 8]. For that reason, the highly technological sectors have been reluctant to use large amounts of recycled plastic, fearing a significant reduction of the material performance and thus, making painted parts virtually not recyclable. In addition, to allow its reuse, impurities must be separated from the component, adding an additional cost than just a mere mechanical recycling.

To separate the paint from the thermoplastic, different treatments are available, including chemical, mechanical and physical treatments [8]. Chemical methods (alkali boiling, organic salt, etc.) are cost efficient, but they are a very destructive technique that uses very aggressive and hazardous chemicals for the environment [7, 9]. Mechanical methods often consist of abrasive techniques (file grinding, high pressure water jet, sandblasting, etc.) but they are very low energy efficient and require time and a high labour force, leading to bad large-scale application [8]. The Physical recycling consists of a re-extrusion process by using melt filters to separate paint residues from the melted thermoplastic. Besides its simplicity, they are very energy-consuming, and they cannot separate the paint from the thermoplastic efficiently, leading to a lower quality recycled material. In a similar conclusion, Zhang and Chen [10] found that the conventional methods are inefficient, expensive and unsuitable for large-scale production. Hence, new, sustainable, efficient, and attractive to the industry methods for removing the coating must be developed to introduce recycled plastics parts into a circular economy [11]. Many publications refer to the CreaSolv® process (CreaCycle GmbH, Germany), a solvent-based technology that is suitable for the recycling of thermoplastics [12, 13] and other materials containing hazardous chemicals [14, 15]. Debonding on demand by using a reactive filler is another current trend for the industry. Functional fillers can be activated by a trigger or stimulus (temperature, UV light, electromagnetism, etc.) after which the adhesive joint is disassembled and thus allows the separation of the materials [3, 16]. One commercial solution is called INDAR Inside®, which involves formulating new adhesives or reformulating commercial adhesives with the introduction of some additives that upon heating at a specified temperature, the additives start to decompose and release gases which migrate by diffusion from the bulk adhesive to interfaces generating

local stresses leading to debonding of the joint [3]. This kind of additives are commonly known as thermally expandable particles (TEPs) [17].

In our previous study XXXXXXXX, it demonstrated the negative impact of the coating impurities and increasing reprocessing cycles on the mechanical properties of ABS and ABS/PC samples. Here, it was evaluated the effect of a triggered debonding on demand process on the mechanical performance of ABS materials. The results expect to provide an insight into the potential reusability of automotive plastic products. The ascribed project (DECOAT) aims to develop efficient systems to remove coatings at the end-of-life of the part, to reduce the damage and promote the use of recycled material in high-tech applications.

3. Materials and Methods

To perform the present study, ABS Elix H605 Black (Elix polymers, Tarragona Spain) was used as the polymer. Polymer pellets were molded using an injection molding machine Engel Victory 350Tn (ENGEL, Austria), to obtain 3 kinds of samples according to the testing needs: Tensile strength (ISO-527-2 type A), impact strength (ISO-179-2) and plates of 110x160x3 mm following ISO 2409 standard for the trigger exposure experiment. An average of 5 samples was reported. INDAR® (Rescoll Technological Center, France) was used as a debonding on demand coating.

3.1. Method to determine the effect of the debonding process on the plastic material.

During the recycling process of coated parts proposed in this study, the debonding procedure itself is of importance. Some debonding/cleaning procedures can affect the properties of the material. The method studied here includes the use of a temperature triggering system, which consists of an industrial adhesive debonding technology which activates through temperature by migrating additives that provokes the disassembly from the substrate, thus removing the coating. The heating trigger coating systems consists of a temperature exposure of 150°C for 5 minutes. The process for debonding is showed in **Figure 1**. In this first approach, uncoated plate samples were exposed to the trigger and then reprocess them, to manufacture tensile and impact samples (**Figure 2**). The objective is to study the material behavior after the reprocessing and temperature trigger effect.

Figure 1. Scheme of the debonding procedure by functional adhesive unions.

Figure 2. Experimental procedure to evaluate the debonding trigger effect on the properties of plastic.

3.2. Method to determine the ageing resistance of the debondable coatings.

In this study, the additives and primers triggered by temperature are designed to react at 120°C or more, so that the coating can be removed in a short time of exposure (commonly several minutes). Although such high temperatures are unlikely to occur during the part's lifespan, it is possible to reach relatively high temperatures (up to 80°C, inside the car cabin) for an extended period of time (hours) due to direct sun exposure. Temperature fluctuations can also occur abruptly due to the alternating day and night cycles. Those environmental conditions could potentially lead to some unexpected coating debonding before the end-of-life, which will invalidate the modified coating in demanding applications such as automotive or electronic industry.

In order to check the coating resistance, several coated samples with the INDAR® debonding system were exposed to the same ageing test described in our previous study XXXX. Then, a crosshatch test was performed to evaluate the coating resistance. The crosshatch was performed in 3 different areas on each sample, with a spacing cuts of 1 mm. Then, the tested area was slightly brushed, and a tape was placed on it and pulled off with an angle of 60° (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3. Crosshatch test.

A visual inspection was performed, and samples were evaluated following the classification below. Only a) or b) results were allowed:

- a) The edges of the incisions are perfectly smooth; none of the squares of the grid is detached.
- b) Detachment of small scales of the coating at the intersections of the incisions, which affects about 5% of the grid part.
- c) The coating has detached along the edges and/or at the intersections of the incisions and affects significantly more than 5% up to about 15% of the grid area.

3.3. Method to determine the performance of the recycling process.

ABS was subjected to a complete recycling process including: a) Heat and clean coated ABS parts with INDAR®, b) Pelletize the cleaned ABS (recycled) and mix them with 70% virgin ABS, c) Extrusion of 30% recycled content ABS + 1.5% additive to transform into pellets again and d) Injections of recycled pellets and testing. The samples were classified according to the below:

Table 1. Samples classification for the complete recycling process.

Sample	Description
ABS	Virgin ABS
ABS1C	ABS after one reprocessing cycle (Recycled)
ABS1C30	ABS including 30% of recycled ABS*
ABS1CR	ABS after INDAR® debonding and reprocessed with additive*
ABS2CR	ABS after INDAR® debonding and reprocessed second time with additive*

*Selected % based un previous studies XXX. **Including 1.5 wt% additive for stabilization

4. Results

4.1. Assessment of the debonding process effect

The samples were manufactured following the procedure explained in section 3.1 (**Figure 2**) and then tested for tensile and impact strength. Results are showed in **Table 2** and **Figure S1**. Comparison was made with the reference recycled material after one reprocessing cycle (ABS1C) since the material was exposed to an additional reprocessing step. As shown in **Table 2**, ABSC1 showed higher results in both tensile and impact strength. This is commonly an effect of the reorientation of the macromolecular chains that produced and increasing loading capacity in the material [18]. On the other hand, exposed ABS to the INDAR® trigger shows a loss of tensile properties when compared to ABS1C of about 13% of the performance. The additional reprocessing effect could led to thermo-oxidation of ABS which produces loss of mechanical properties by degradation in the polybutadiene phase [19]. In the case of impact strength, ABS showed a high resilience to the trigger of the INDAR® treatment, losing only 2% of the performance. The proposed debonding method showed to be successful in retaining most of the mechanical performance of ABS, being highlighted on the impact strength.

Table 2. Tensile and impact strength results of ABS after selected debonding processes.

Mechanical performance	ABS	ABS1C	INDAR®
Tensile modulus (Mpa)	2407.4 ± 84.8	2543.1 ± 136.7	2212.5 ± 88.0
Impact (KJ/m²)	18.43 ± 0.25	18.29 ± 0.21	17.87 ± 0.77

4.2. Performance of debonding coating after ageing

In order to test the resistance of the coated material after the end of life of the product after exposure to the debonding trigger (temperature), a crosshatch test after the ageing was performed. The objective is to test the endurance of the paint along the lifespan of the sample. The samples coated with INDAR® primer were exposed to the ageing test, as described in section 3.2. For each material, the crosshatch test was done on 3 exposed samples and in 2 non-exposed ones to be used as a reference (**Table 3**). As reported, most of the measured points reached the needed mark (“a” or “b”). Therefore, INDAR® primer resists the ageing test without unexpected debonding.

Table 3. Crosshatch test results for ABS samples.

Material	Reference						Aged samples								
	Sample 1			Sample 2			Sample 1			Sample 2			Sample 3		
	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III
ABS	a	a	a	b	a	a	a	a	a	a	a	a	a	a	a

4.3. Assessment of the performance of the recycling process

The samples were manufactured following the procedure explained in section 3.3 and then tested for tensile and impact strength. Results are showed in **Table 4** and **Figure S2**. It can be observed that the reprocessing (ABS1C) and introduction of recycled content (ABS1C30) could increase the tensile strength due to reorientation of the macromolecular chains [18]. The first cleaning and reprocessing (ABS1CR) showed lower performance than the reference by about 19%. The repetition of this process (ABS2CR) obtained lower results than ABS1C as well by 17%. The continuous degradation of by the reprocessing is one of the most important factors affecting the mechanical performance of reused plastics [20]. In the case of impact strength, ABS1CR showed almost no impact from the recycling process whereas ABS2CR, the performance decreased by 6.5%. Similar to the results of **Table 2**, the impact strength of ABS was more resilient than the tensile. It was reported that the increasing presence of TEPs; probably due to the impurities of previous reprocessing cycles, decrease the mechanical performance of the material [21]. The presence of increasing impurities due to the imperfect cleaning of the process as reported in our previous study **XXX**, led to cohesive failure on the structure of the material via cavitation [22, 8, 5]. Overall, the reused ABS material can maintain about 85% of the original tensile and 93% of the impact strength with respect to the virgin one. These results confirm the reusability of ABS after debonding and recycling by selected procedures.

Table 4. Tensile and impact strength results of ABS after the recycling process.

Sample	Tensile modulus (Mpa)	Impact strength (KJ/m ²)
ABS	2407 ± 85	18.43 ± 0.25

ABS1C	2543 ± 137	18.29 ± 0.21
ABS1C30	2538 ± 166	18.67 ± 0.49
ABS1CR	2069 ± 298	18.22 ± 0.40
ABS2CR	2121 ± 164	17.10 ± 0.25

5. Conclusion

In this study, a methodology to evaluate the recyclability for automotive ABS parts was performed. A debondable by demand coating (INDAR®) was used as a tool to allow easy separation of the components when a determined temperature is reached. The mechanical performance (tensile and impact strength) of the materials was compared with the

- The exposure to the trigger conditions of the debondable coating led to a depleting tensile strength. The impact strength was almost maintained. Degradation on the polybutadiene phase of ABS was ascribed as the responsible for this result.
- The crosshatch test was performed to evaluate the primer resistance to the ageing process, showing sufficient fulfillment.
- A complete recycling process was designed and completed up to two reprocessing cycles. Addition of a 30% recycled material and debondable coating was included. The first batch showed a loss of 17% of the tensile strength but maintained the impact performance. The second batch showed decreasing properties by a loss of 19% of the tensile strength and 6.5% of the impact resistance. Degradation by reprocessing as well as the presence of coating impurities could explain this performance.

Overall, the recycling process presented here proved to be of value for the automotive industry and the concerns about the reuse and circular economy of plastics into the market.

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